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Simulation Studies on the Growth of Microorganisms in Batch Processes under Secondary Substrate Limitation

SSGMBPSSL

Data Management Plan (DMP)

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Deliverable abstract

This deliverable is the final Data Management Plan (DMP) for the Simulation Studies on the Growth of Microorganisms in Batch Processes under Secondary Substrate Limitation project, delivered on 30.04.2024. The DMP addresses the relevant aspects of the management of data and other outputs produced by the project.

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TERMINOLOGY

<https://eosc-portal.eu/glossary>

Acronym	Definition
DMP	Data Management Plan
CSV	Comma Separated Values
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
FAIR	FAIR-Principles: Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
MB	Megabyte
PDF	Portable Document Format
WP	Work Package

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1. Executive Summary

1.1. Introduction

A data management plan (DMP) is a structured document that keeps record of what research data is created or reused and what happens to that data during and after a project. It helps with planning the research process and defining responsibilities in a research project involving several researchers or institutions. For writing this DMP, we followed the [Horizon Europe DMP template](#).

Michael Leander Büchs acted as the data manager in charge of the actions described by this DMP.

The purpose of this project is to generate data using an existing mathematical model from the domain of biochemical engineering and document the generated data according to the FAIR principles. The mathematical model replicates the growth and substrate consumption of a biological organism in a bioreactor. More specifically, the mathematical model describes an organism requiring both Glucose and Threonine as a substrate. Threonine is dosed in small quantities and thus is the first of the two substrates to deplete. Depletion of Threonine causes the organism to enter the state of secondary substrate limitation. In this state, the growth of the organism is inhibited and the organism switches into a maintenance metabolism. Additionally to the growth and substrate consumption, the model replicates the oxygen transfer required to keep the organism alive. In this experiment, the mathematical model will be simulated for three initial concentrations of Threonine, thus creating three distinct data sets. The mathematical model used in this experiment was developed at the Chair of Biochemical Process Engineering at RWTH Aachen ([ROR](#)).

1.2. Data Summary

- Will you re-use any existing data and what will you re-use it for? State the reasons if re-use of any existing data has been considered but discarded.
- What types and formats of data will the project generate or re-use?
- What is the purpose of the data generation or re-use and its relation to the objectives of the project?
- What is the expected size of the data that you intend to generate or re-use?
- What is the origin/provenance of the data, either generated or re-used?
- To whom might your data be useful ('data utility'), outside your project?

Produced datasets:

dataset ID	title	type	format	estimated volume	contains sensitive data
P1	raw_data_to_FAIR_conversion.ipynb	Source code	Jupyter Notebook	100 MB	no
P2	simulation1_parameters.json	Structured text	JSON	100 MB	no
P3	simulation1_time_series_data.csv	Structured text	CSV	100 MB	no

dataset ID	title	type	format	estimated volume	contains sensitive data
P4	simulation2_parameters.json	Structured text	JSON	100 MB	no
P5	simulation2_time_series_data.csv	Structured text	CSV	100 MB	no
P6	simulation3_parameters.json	Structured text	JSON	100 MB	no
P7	simulation3_time_series_data.csv	Structured text	CSV	100 MB	no

Reused datasets:

dataset ID	title	PID (e.g. DOI) or source	rights (e.g. license)	contains sensitive data
R1	simulation1_output_time_series_data.txt	Source: Mathematical model from the Chair of Biochemical Engineering of RWTH Aachen (ROR) implemented in Model Maker	CC-BY	no
R2	simulation2_output_time_series_data.txt	Source: Mathematical model from the Chair of Biochemical Engineering of RWTH Aachen (ROR) implemented in Model Maker	CC-BY	no
R3	simulation3_output_time_series_data.txt	Source: Mathematical model from the Chair of Biochemical Engineering of RWTH Aachen (ROR) implemented in Model Maker	CC-BY	no
R4	secondary_substrate_limitation.mod	Source: Personal contacts to the Chair of Biochemical Process	None	yes

		Engineering, RWTH Aachen University (ROR).		
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1.3. Methods and software used for data generation and reuse

As mentioned in the project description, the mathematical model used in this project was developed at the Chair of Biochemical Engineering at RWTH Aachen (ROR). It combines kinetic equations for the growth of the organism with a mass-transfer model for the supply of Oxygen. The resulting model is a differential-algebraic system of equations. Solving this system of equations requires implementing the equations into an appropriate software. As of now, the model is implemented in Model Maker, a domain-specific and license-bound equation solver. The Model Maker model is called `secondary_substrate_limitation.mod` and is referenced in the section 'Reused Data'. Since the model equations must not be made public, the scope of this work is restricted to simulating the model for three common initial concentrations of threonine. To run the simulation, the Model Maker model requires the following three types of input parameters:

- 1.) Natural constants, e.g. the maximal growth rate 'muemax' of the organism. These parameters must be taken from previous measurements and are already included in the model. Since modification to the organism could change these constants, they are considered as input parameters, even though they will remain constant over the creation of the three data sets.
- 2.) Experiment-specific parameters, e.g. the initial concentrations of substrate S_0 and threonine Thr_0 or the specific aeration rate qG (check the README.pdf of the data repository for extensive definition of variables & units). For the purpose of this experiment, Thr_0 will be varied with all other things equal.
- 3.) Parameters of the equation-solver, e.g. the numerical method used to solve the equation system. Since Model Maker does not allow for an automated extraction of these parameters, they were entered into an excel ('model_input_documentation.xlsx') template manually and then processed into a more machine actionable format by a python script implemented in a jupyter notebook ('raw_data_to_FAIR_conversion.ipynb').

The output of the Model Maker model is time-series data. The time-series data contains the concentrations of both substrates and the organism. The time-series data also contains data on the dissolved Oxygen concentration, as well as the Oxygen Transfer Rate (OTR), a measure of the flow rate of oxygen into the organisms. The time-series data is extracted from the Model Maker model using the software's export functionality, which yields a .txt file ('simulationX_output_time_series_data.txt'). A Python script implemented as a Jupyter Notebook ('raw_data_to_FAIR_conversion.ipynb') then saves the time-series data into .csv format. The Python script also converts the model parameters from .xlsx format into a JSON file, since this format is more machine actionable.

1.4. Foreseeable research uses and /or users

Researchers and educators who are interested in the mechanics of secondary substrate limitation in biochemical engineering.

2. FAIR data

2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

- Will data be identified by a persistent identifier?
- Will rich metadata be provided to allow discovery? What metadata will be created? What disciplinary or general standards will be followed? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how.
- Will search keywords be provided in the metadata to optimize the possibility for discovery and then potential re-use?
- Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?

We will make our data findable by uploading it to a data repository that provides a persistent identifier and adding relevant metadata. The repository will provide means for harvesting the metadata, including its machine-actionable representation.

The output of this project consists of data and source code. The output is stored in two locations. The first location is the TU Wien Research Data Repository test instance ([DOI](#), [Weblink](#)) (from now on referred to as 'data repository'). The repository stores all data related to the project. The second location is a GitHub repository ([DOI](#)) (from now on referred to as 'code repository').

The data repository contains two folders and one excel file. The first folder is called '00-raw-model-output-data'. This folder contains the raw time-series data in .txt format as it was extracted from the Model Maker model. The second folder is called '01-processed-model-output-data'. This folder contains one sub-folder for each simulation. Each simulation subfolder contains a .json and a .csv file. The .json file documents the respective input parameters in a machine-actionable form. The .csv file documents the time-series data in a machine-actionable form. The excel file is the file containing the input parameters of the simulation runs in a human-readable form. It also serves as documentation of the model input parameters. All contents of the data repository were created during the project and the version present in the data repository is regarded as the sole and final version.

The code repository is structured as a regular GitHub repository. The development of the source code can be reconstructed through the respective commits. Meaningful commit messages were used. Further information on the content and structure of the code repository, as well as the functioning of the code can be found in the code repositories' README and respective code comments. The DOI of the code repository references version v1.0 of the code. A version with additional references to this data management plan and the data repository can be found in the latest commit of the main branch.

As there are no domain-specific metadata standards applicable for simulation studies, the data repository provides a central README on repository-level. The README documents:

- 1.) All information that can be made public about the biochemical system modeled
- 2.) Definition and explanation of model variables

Additionally to the repository-level README file, the excel template for manual documentation of input parameters documents all 'hard-facts' relevant for replicating the experiment, given the model equations. This will help others to identify, discover and reuse our data.

Additionally, we will provide common metadata such as title, description, or keywords when publishing data. In this case, we will follow the default template provided by the repository, such as Data Cite Metadata or Dublin Core.

As far as possible, we used controlled vocabularies for our data to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability and machine-actionability.

2.2. Making data accessible

Repository:

- Will the data be deposited in a trusted repository?
- Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository where your data will be deposited?
- Does the repository ensure that the data is assigned an identifier? Will the repository resolve the identifier to a digital object?

Data:

- Will all data be made openly available? If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restricted access conditions), explain why, clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from intentional restrictions. Note that in multi-beneficiary projects it is also possible for specific beneficiaries to keep their data closed if opening their data goes against their legitimate interests or other constraints as per the Grant Agreement.
- If an embargo is applied to give time to publish or seek protection of the intellectual property (e.g. patents), specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.
- Will the data be accessible through a free and standardized access protocol?
- If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided to the data, both during and after the end of the project?
- How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?
- Is there a need for a data access committee (e.g. to evaluate/approve access requests to personal/sensitive data)?

Metadata:

- Will metadata be made openly available and licenced under a public domain dedication CC0, as per the Grant Agreement? If not, please clarify why. Will metadata contain information to enable the user to access the data?
- How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available?
- Will documentation or reference about any software be needed to access or read the data be included? Will it be possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

We will make our data accessible by providing open access to data, wherever possible. In cases where open access is not possible, we will provide meaningful metadata plus contact information for access requests.

dataset ID	access conditions	restrictions / embargo reasons	estimated publication date	location for publication (repository)	PID	license
P1	Open		2024-02-29	GitHub	DOI	MIT
P2	Open		2024-02-29	TU Wien Research Data	DOI	PD

dataset ID	access conditions	restrictions / embargo reasons	estimated publication date	location for publication (repository)	PID	license
					Weblink	
P3	Open		2024-02-29	TU Wien Research Data	DOI Weblink	PD
P4	Open		2024-02-29	TU Wien Research Data	DOI Weblink	PD
P5	Open		2024-02-29	TU Wien Research Data	DOI Weblink	PD
P6	Open		2024-02-29	TU Wien Research Data	DOI Weblink	PD
P7	Open		2024-02-29	TU Wien Research Data	DOI Weblink	PD

Repository description:

TU Wien Research Data is an institutional repository of TU Wien to enable storing, sharing and publishing of digital objects, in particular research data. It facilitates the funders' requirements for open access to research data and the FAIR principles by making research output findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable. A DOI is assigned to each dataset published in TU Wien Research Data. This service is developed by the TU Wien Center for Research Data Management and hosted by TU.it. <https://researchdata.tuwien.at/>

GitHub is the best place to share code with friends, co-workers, classmates, and complete strangers. Over three million people use GitHub to build amazing things together. With the collaborative features of GitHub.com, our desktop and mobile apps, and GitHub Enterprise, it has never been easier for individuals and teams to write better code, faster. Originally founded by Tom Preston-Werner, Chris Wanstrath, and PJ Hyett to simplify sharing code, GitHub has grown into the largest code host in the world. <https://github.com>

Methods or software needed to access and use data: An operating system able to open .json, .csv and .xlsx.

2.3. Making data interoperable

- What data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable to allow data exchange and re-use within and across disciplines? Will you follow community-endorsed interoperability best practices? Which ones?

- In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies? Will you openly publish the generated ontologies or vocabularies to allow reusing, refining, or extending them?
- Will your data include qualified references to other data (e.g. other data from your project, or datasets from previous research)?

We made our data interoperable by providing and describing data in a way that is common within our domain of biochemical engineering. As far as possible, we used controlled vocabularies for our data to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability and machine-actionability. We provided extensive documentation for all our datasets.

2.4. Increase data re-use

- How will you provide documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use (e.g. readme files with information on methodology, codebooks, data cleaning, analyses, variable definitions, units of measurement, etc.)?
- Will your data be made freely available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible? Will your data be licensed using standard reuse licenses, in line with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement?
- Will the data produced in the project be useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?
- Will the provenance of the data be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards?
- Describe all relevant data quality assurance processes.
- Further to the FAIR principles, DMPs should also address research outputs other than data, and should carefully consider aspects related to the allocation of resources, data security and ethical aspects.

We will make our data reusable by adding metadata and comprehensive Readme files to all published datasets. The descriptions include details on the methodology used, analytical, and procedural information. In case of publication, licenses for code and data are always assigned and clearly marked. The digital research data obtained will be published Open Access under a Creative Commons CC BY license, provided there are no data protection concerns.

The aforementioned documentation provides all information needed to recreate (and thus validate) the simulations, with the exception of the (not published) model equations. Access to the model equations can be requested from the person marked as contact in the first section of this data management plan. Access allowance to the model equations will be discussed on a case-specific basis and decided in conjunction with the representatives of the Chair of Biochemical Process Engineering at RWTH Aachen ([ROR](#)). All information required to recreate the conversion of the simulation data into the fair format is contained in the aforementioned documentation and can be validated by anyone from the general public.

The following data quality checks will be done: The time-series are solely the result of a computation and thus not prone to measurement errors. The extraction and processing of this data was handled using the automated extraction function of Model Maker and using the code provided in the code repository. The data extraction of Model Maker lies under the scrutiny of a commercial software and is regarded as infallible. The mechanisms of the data processing happening in the python script are transparent to anyone trying to recreate the results. The

input parameters, in contrast, had to be documented manually. To ensure correct copying, the extracted input parameters were checked with the 'four-eyes-principle'.

3. Other research outputs

- In addition to the management of data, beneficiaries should also consider and plan for the management of other research outputs that may be generated or re-used throughout their projects. Such outputs can be either digital (e.g. software, workflows, protocols, models, etc.) or physical (e.g. new materials, antibodies, reagents, samples, etc.).
- Beneficiaries should consider which of the questions pertaining to FAIR data above, can apply to the management of other research outputs, and should strive to provide sufficient detail on how their research outputs will be managed and shared, or made available for re-use, in line with the FAIR principles.

4. Allocation of resources

- What will the costs be for making data or other research outputs FAIR in your project (e.g. direct and indirect costs related to storage, archiving, re-use, security, etc.)?
- How will these be covered? Note that costs related to research data/output management are eligible as part of the Horizon Europe grant (if compliant with the Grant Agreement conditions)
- Who will be responsible for data management in your project?
- How will long term preservation be ensured? Discuss the necessary resources to accomplish this (costs and potential value, who decides and how, what data will be kept and for how long)?

There are no costs dedicated to data management and ensuring that data will be FAIR.

Cost name	Cost type	Description	Unit	Value
Estimated total costs				0

The data manager directed the data management process overall, with Michael Leander Büchs being responsible for ensuring metadata production, day-to-day cross-checks, back-up and other quality control activities are maintained.

5. Data security

- What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)?
- Will the data be safely stored in trusted repositories for long term preservation and curation?

5.1. Storage and backup facilities

For the duration of the project, storage and backup of data was ensured by the project manager.

P2 (simulation1_parameters.json), P3 (simulation1_time_series_data.csv), P4 (simulation2_parameters.json), P5 (simulation2_time_series_data.csv), P6 (simulation3_parameters.json), P7 (simulation3_time_series_data.csv), R1 (simulation1_output_time_series_data.txt), R2 (simulation2_output_time_series_data.txt), R3 (simulation3_output_time_series_data.txt) are stored on TUfiles test instance: TUfiles is a central and readily available network drive with daily backups and regular snapshots provided by TU.it. It is suitable for storing data with moderate access requirements, but high availability demands that allows full control of allocating authorisations. Only authorized staff members will have access.

P1 (raw_data_to_FAIR_conversion.ipynb) is stored on GitHub. Institutional storage is not used, since GitHub represents the industry-standard for code repositories.

5.2. Data security and protection of sensitive data

We pay strict attention to compliance with the relevant institutional and national data protection policies.

In this project there will be sensitive data in dataset R4 (secondary_substrate_limitation.mod). To ensure that storage and transfer of sensitive data is safe, additional security measures such as individual log-in and password is taken. Only everyone listed as involved in the project in section 1 of this DMP is authorised to access sensitive data.

Access to data during research:

dataset ID	selected project members	all other project members	the public
P1	writing	writing	reading only
P2	writing	writing	reading only
P3	writing	writing	reading only
P4	writing	writing	reading only
P5	writing	writing	reading only
P6	writing	writing	reading only
P7	writing	writing	reading only
R1	writing	writing	reading only
R2	writing	writing	reading only

dataset ID	selected project members	all other project members	the public
R3	writing	writing	reading only
R4	writing	writing	no access

All incidents will be handled individually by an incident response team, composed of Michael Leander Büchs, that is maintaining the affected service.

5.3. Long-term preservation and deletion of data

dataset ID	location for long-term storage	minimum retention period (≥ 10 years)
P1	GitHub	10 years
P2	TU Wien Research Data	10 years
P3	TU Wien Research Data	10 years
P4	TU Wien Research Data	10 years
P5	TU Wien Research Data	10 years
P6	TU Wien Research Data	10 years
P7	TU Wien Research Data	10 years

6. Ethical and legal issues

- Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing? These can also be discussed in the context of the ethics review. If relevant, include references to ethics deliverables and ethics chapter in the Description of the Action (DoA).
- Will informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation be included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?

6.1. Personal data

At this stage, it is not foreseen to process any personal data in the project. If this changes, advice will be sought from the data protection specialist at TU Wien, and the DMP will be updated.

6.2. Intellectual property rights and ownership

There are no legal restrictions on the processing and disclosure of our data.

6.3. Ethical issues

No particular ethical issue is foreseen with the data to be used or produced by the project. This section will be updated if issues arise.

7. Other issues

- Do you, or will you, make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management? If yes, which ones (please list and briefly describe them)?

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